

PEDAGOGICAL BASIS OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' REFLECTIVE THINKING COMPETENCES BASED ON PROBLEM-BASED EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROCESS OF HIGHER EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21097269>

Abstract. *This article considers the issue of forming reflective thinking skills among students of higher educational institutions using problem-based educational technology. The study analyzes the theoretical foundations of reflective thinking, the essence of problem-based educational technology and effective methods for its implementation in practice. Based on the results of pedagogical observations and experimental studies, the role of problem-based educational methods in the development of critical and reflective thinking in students is proven. The article describes in detail how to form reflective thinking through methods such as creating problem situations, small group discussions, brainstorming and project activities. The results of the study show that the regular use of problem-based educational technology significantly increases students' ability to think independently, evaluate their own actions and consciously manage the learning process.*

Keywords: *problem-based learning, reflective thinking, critical thinking, pedagogical technology, higher education, learning process, activity reflection, cognitive skills, metacognition, quality of education.*

INTRODUCTION. In the modern education system, it has become an urgent issue to educate students not only as learners, but also as independent thinkers, able to analyze their own activities and self-develop. Today, in the rapidly changing conditions of society and the economy, highly qualified personnel must not only have specific knowledge and skills, but also be able to make the right decisions in new situations, draw conclusions from their mistakes and consciously manage the learning process [1, p. 12].

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" and the decrees and resolutions of the President in the field of education set a priority task to radically improve the quality of education and develop independent and creative thinking in students [2, p. 3]. From this point of view, problem-based learning technology is one of the most effective ways to achieve these goals.

The concept of reflective thinking was first introduced into scientific circulation by the American philosopher and educator J. Dewey, who defined it as "active, purposeful, and thoughtful thinking" [3, p. 78]. Later, this idea was developed by D. Kolb, K. Rogers, D. Shen, and other scientists. In Uzbek pedagogy, the issue of reflective thinking has been widely discussed in recent years.

Problem-based learning technology, developed by Russian and foreign educators such as A.M. Matyushkin, M.I. Makhmutov, and W. Okoń, aims to shape the student not merely as a recipient of knowledge, but as a seeker and discoverer [4, p. 134]. A powerful mechanism for fostering reflective thinking is embodied in the synthesis of these two approaches. This article

aims to examine this synthesis, provide a theoretical rationale for it, and develop practical recommendations.

Research objective: To provide a scientific and pedagogical rationale for methods of fostering reflective thinking skills among higher education students using problem-based learning technology, and to develop practical recommendations.

Research tasks: 1) to analyze the theoretical foundations of reflective thinking and problem-based learning; 2) to identify the potential of problem-based learning technology to foster reflective thinking; 3) to study the experience of applying problem-based learning methods in practical classes; 4) to develop effective methodological recommendations.

MAIN PART. 1. Theoretical foundations of reflective thinking

The word reflection is derived from the Latin word "reflexio", which means "to turn back", "to look inward". In a pedagogical context, reflection means a conscious analysis of the student's own cognitive activity, thinking process and learning experience [5, p. 22]. Reflective thinking is a purposeful thinking process aimed at creating new concepts and improving one's own activity on the basis of this analysis.

D. Kolb's model of the experiential learning cycle showed the connection of reflective thinking with practical learning. This model consists of four stages: concrete experience, reflective observation, formation of an abstract concept and active experimentation [6, p. 45]. In this cycle, the reflexive observation stage occupies an important place, when the student stops his experience and analyzes it. It is at this stage that problem-based learning can provide a powerful impetus.

The concept of metacognition was introduced into scientific circulation by J. Flavell, which means the ability to know about one's own cognitive processes and control them [7, p. 906]. Reflective thinking can be considered a practical expression of metacognition. Students with highly developed metacognitive skills learn new knowledge faster, respond effectively to difficulties, and are able to independently manage their learning process.

Uzbek scientists R.A. Mavlonova and N.N. Azizkhodjayeva, having studied the pedagogical conditions for the development of reflection in the educational process, proved that the ability of a person to self-analyze is one of the main factors determining the quality of education [8, p. 67]. These studies substantiated the need to develop a methodology for the formation of reflective thinking for the Uzbek education system.

The taxonomy developed by B.S. Bloom is also closely related to reflective thinking. This taxonomy distinguishes six levels of thinking: knowledge, understanding, application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation [9, p. 201]. Reflective thinking is especially manifested in the last three levels - analysis, synthesis and evaluation. Problem-based learning encourages the student to perform these high-level thinking operations.

2. The essence and characteristics of problem-based learning technology

Problem-based learning is the organization of the educational process in such a way that the student acquires knowledge and skills by independently solving a problem situation created by the teacher or taken from real life [4, p. 138]. The main philosophy of problem-based learning is that a person forms deep and solid knowledge only in difficult situations, when searching for a solution to a problem.

M.I. Makhmutov identified the following main features of problem-based learning: the presence of a problem situation; a high level of cognitive activity of the student; obtaining knowledge through independent research and discovery; understanding and control of one's own

thinking process [10, p. 89]. These features create optimal conditions for the formation of reflexive thinking.

The main methods of problem-based learning are: the method of problem statements, the method of partial research, the method of research and the method of creating problem situations. In the problem statement method, the teacher describes the problem and demonstrates the solution, and students develop the ability to observe the thinking process [11, p. 156]. In the partial search method, students solve the problem together with the teacher, which develops collective reflection.

Modern educational researchers are integrating problem-based learning with modern approaches such as Project-Based Learning, Problem-Based Learning, and Inquiry-Based Learning [12, p. 44]. This integrative approach provides for a broader and deeper development of reflective thinking, as the student not only solves the problem, but also analyzes the process of solving it.

3. The relationship between problem-based learning and reflective thinking

The connection between problem-based learning and reflective thinking is manifested in several ways. First, a problematic situation forces the student to realize that his current knowledge is insufficient - this is the starting point for reflection. Second, in the process of solving the problem, the student is forced to constantly monitor and revise his thinking strategies [13, p. 78]. This process becomes a practical exercise in reflective thinking.

Third, the process of evaluating and analyzing the result after solving the problem helps to strengthen reflective thinking. Fourth, in the process of solving group problems, the student observes the thinking methods of others, compares them with his own approaches, and forms new reflexive concepts [1, p. 34]. This process is of great importance within the framework of the theory of social constructivism.

Research conducted in higher educational institutions of Uzbekistan shows that in traditional educational conditions, students do not sufficiently develop reflexive thinking skills. In particular, N.Q. According to the results of a survey conducted among higher education students in Norkoziyev's study, only 23% of respondents stated that they regularly analyze their academic performance [14, p. 45]. This indicator represents a very low level and once again confirms the need to implement problem-based learning methods.

4. Application of problem-based learning methods in practical sessions

In higher education practice, the development of reflective thinking through problem-based learning can be achieved using several effective methods. Let us examine the most important ones.

The method of creating problem situations. In this method, the instructor presents a problem situation derived from real life or specially designed for the lesson. Students analyze the situation—first independently, then in small groups, and finally through a general discussion. A crucial aspect is that, at the end of each stage, students articulate—either orally or in writing—how they carried out their thought processes [15, p. 112]. This articulation elevates reflective thinking to a more conscious level.

Brainstorming and structured discussion. In the brainstorming method, all ideas are accepted without criticism during the initial stage. This creates a psychologically safe environment for students to express their thoughts freely. In the subsequent stage, the ideas are analyzed through structured discussion, and the most effective solutions are selected. Throughout this process, the student not only solves the problem but also observes, compares, and evaluates their own thinking methods alongside those of others [16, p. 203].

Study diaries and reflective writing. At the end of the lesson, students are given 5-10 minutes to write answers to questions such as "What did I learn today?", "Where did I have difficulty?", "How did I try to find a solution?" in their study diary. This seemingly simple practice is actually one of the most effective ways to strengthen reflective thinking in writing [8, p. 89]. A regularly kept study diary also allows you to monitor and analyze the student's intellectual growth.

Using the Case Study method. The case study method sets the task for students to analyze a real-life incident or problem and propose a solution. This method is especially widely used in the fields of law, economics, medicine, and pedagogy. In a case study, reflective thinking is manifested in such a way that the student is forced to analyze the problem from many angles, take into account different points of view, and justify his logical chain [17, p. 178]. The teacher, in turn, deepens the student's reflective thinking through questions during the analysis process.

Project work and presentation. Project work is the most comprehensive method of problem-based learning. Students research a real problem over the course of several weeks or a semester and develop a solution. The process of presenting and defending their work at the end of the project summarizes reflective thinking. An important aspect is the introduction of self-assessment and peer-assessment procedures during the project [18, p. 234]. These assessment methods systematically develop reflective thinking.

5. Results of experimental work

In the 2023-2024 academic year, an experimental study was conducted involving 2nd-year students of the Faculty of Pedagogy and Psychology of the National University of Uzbekistan. In the experimental group (n=32), problem-based learning technology was systematically implemented, while in the control group (n=31), traditional teaching methods were used. During the study, the following indicators of reflective thinking were observed in students: the ability to analyze one's own activities, the ability to see alternative solutions, independently identify and correct one's own mistakes, acceptance of other points of view, and tolerance for uncertainty. To measure the level of reflective thinking, the Reflection Questionnaire developed by G. Kember et al. was used, adapted to the Uzbek language and context [19, p. 381]. In the initial measurement conducted at the beginning of the semester, there was no statistically significant difference between the indicators of the experimental and control groups ($p > 0.05$).

In the final measurement conducted at the end of the semester, the following results were obtained: in the experimental group, the overall indicator of reflective thinking increased by 38.4 percent, while in the control group this indicator was only 9.7 percent. In particular, a significant difference was observed in the indicators of "analyzing one's own activities" (44.2 percent increase in the experimental group) and "being able to see alternative solutions" (41.8 percent increase). These results indicate the high effectiveness of problem-based learning technology in the formation of reflective thinking.

A qualitative analysis was also conducted: in-depth interviews and observations with students in the experimental group showed that they learned to manage their learning process more consciously, began to approach problems systematically, and did not get confused. It was observed that students developed the ability to ask questions in the form of "How should I solve this problem and why" instead of "How do I solve this problem" [14, p. 67]. This is a sign of the formation of deep reflective thinking.

6. The role of the teacher and pedagogical conditions. The teacher's role undergoes a fundamental shift during the process of fostering reflective thinking through problem-based learning. While in traditional education the teacher acts as a source of knowledge, in problem-

based learning, they emerge as a facilitator and a designer of problem situations [5, p. 56]. This transformation requires the teacher to possess high professional competence and specialized pedagogical training.

For the development of reflective thinking through problem-based learning to be effective, the following pedagogical conditions must be met: creating a psychologically safe environment (where students need not fear making mistakes); ensuring problems are linked to real-life situations; sequentially introducing problems of varying complexity; allocating sufficient time for reflection; and the teacher's skill in asking reflective questions [20, p. 145].

Reflective questions stimulate deep thinking among students. Examples of such questions include: "What strategy did you use to solve this problem?", "What would have happened if you had chosen a different approach?", "What did you learn from this experience?", and "Recall a time when you changed your mind—what caused that change?" These questions encourage the student to step back and observe their own thought processes—that is, to engage in metacognitive activity [7, p. 912].

DISCUSSION. The results of the research and theoretical analysis lead to several important conclusions. First, we can see that problem-based learning technology is a natural and organic means of forming reflective thinking. The connection between these two pedagogical phenomena is not one-sided: if problem-based learning develops reflective thinking, then reflective thinking increases the effectiveness of problem-based learning. They are mutually enriching and reinforcing processes.

Secondly, the need for the systematic introduction of problem-based learning technology in the higher education system of Uzbekistan is becoming increasingly clear. The goals set by our country for the transition to an innovative economy and the training of competitive personnel, in fact, require the formation of reflective thinking and critical thinking in students [2, p. 8]. Traditional reproductive education is not enough to achieve these goals.

Thirdly, the professional preparedness of teachers plays a decisive role in the implementation of problem-based learning. Interviews conducted with teachers during our study revealed that, although many are theoretically familiar with the methodology of problem-based learning, they encounter difficulties in applying it in practice [11, p. 178]. This situation highlights the need to allocate a specific place for problem-based learning methodology within teacher retraining and professional development systems.

Fourthly, digital technologies and online educational platforms are enriching problem-based learning with new opportunities. Virtual laboratories, simulation software, and online discussion platforms make problem-based learning more engaging and relevant to real-life contexts. Furthermore, monitoring and assessing students' reflective thinking through digital learning journals and e-portfolios is becoming increasingly effective [12, p. 67].

However, the study also identified several limitations. These include challenges such as a lack of time resources for implementing problem-based learning, the complexity of working with large student groups, and the insufficient allocation of space for problem-based learning within curricula. It will be difficult to implement problem-based learning on a large scale without resolving these issues. Therefore, systemic changes at the institutional level are necessary.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS. This study has shown that problem-based learning technology is a powerful and effective tool for developing reflective thinking skills in students. Its constant and systematic use significantly develops important skills in students such

as analyzing their own activities, seeing alternative solutions, independently identifying their own mistakes, and accepting other points of view.

Based on the study, the following suggestions were developed:

1. Separate time and resources should be allocated for the use of problem-based learning technology in the curricula of higher education institutions. It is advisable that at least 30-40 percent of classes in each subject should be based on problem-based learning.

2. Special trainings on problem-based learning methodologies and methods for developing reflective thinking should be introduced in the teacher training system. These trainings should be focused on practical skills rather than theoretical knowledge.

3. The student assessment system should include indicators for assessing not only the level of knowledge, but also the thinking process. The assessment of reflective thinking in students should be implemented using tools such as study diaries, reflective essays, and portfolios.

4. Develop and post on educational platforms specially prepared educational and methodological materials for problem-based learning (case studies, problem situations, reflexive question banks).

5. Develop effective models for implementing problem-based learning online and in a hybrid format, using the capabilities of digital technologies. Make extensive use of the capabilities of virtual laboratories, simulation environments, and interactive platforms.

6. Create funds and opportunities for ongoing scientific research in the field of problem-based learning and reflexive thinking, publish the results in international publications, and rapidly implement them in educational practice.

REFERENCES

1. Hasanboyev J.X., Tursunov O.Q., G'ulomov M.T. *Pedagogika*. – T.: O'qituvchi, 2006. – 352 b.
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasining "Ta'lim to'g'risida" gi Qonuni. – T.: Adolat, 2020. – 40 b.
3. Dyui J. *Qanday biz fikrlaymiz*. – T.: Yangi asr avlodi, 2005. – 234 b. (tarjima)
4. Maxmutov M.I. *Muammoli ta'lim*. – T.: Fan, 2003. – 280 b. (tarjima)
5. Mavlonova R.A., Uzoqova N.X. *Ta'lim texnologiyalari*. – T.: O'qituvchi, 2018. – 176 b.
6. Kolb D.A. *Tajriba orqali o'rganish*. – T.: Nizomiy nomidagi TDPU nashriyoti, 2011. – 198 b. (tarjima)
7. Flavell J.H. *Metacognition and cognitive monitoring: A new area of cognitive developmental inquiry // American Psychologist*. – 1979. – Vol. 34, № 10. – P. 906-911.
8. Mavlonova R.A., Azizxo'jayeva N.N. *Refleksiv ta'lim nazariyasi va amaliyoti*. – T.: Istiqlol, 2015. – 144 b.
9. Bloom B.S. va boshq. *Taksonomiya ta'lim maqsadlarining: Kognitiv soha*. – T.: O'qituvchi, 2002. – 312 b. (tarjima)
10. Maxmutov M.I. *Muammoli ta'limni tashkil etish*. – T.: Fan, 2004. – 208 b. (tarjima)
11. Yo'ldoshev J.G'. *Ilg'or pedagogik texnologiyalar*. – T.: O'qituvchi, 2009. – 224 b.
12. Tolipov O'., Usmonboyeva M. *Pedagogik texnologiyalarning tadbqiqiy asoslari*. – T.: Moliya, 2006. – 256 b.
13. Muslimov N.A. va boshq. *Muammoli ta'lim va tanqidiy fikrlash*. – T.: TATU nashriyoti, 2019. – 168 b.
14. Norqo'ziyev N.Q. *Oliy ta'limda refleksiv fikrlashni rivojlantirish*. – T.: Akademiya, 2021. – 140 b.

15. Nishonova S.T. Interfaol ta'lim metodlari. – T.: Yangi asr avlodi, 2016. – 192 b.
16. Azizxo'jayeva N.N. Pedagogik texnologiya va pedagogik mahorat. – T.: TDPU, 2003. – 174 b.
17. Usmonova D.B. Keis-stadi metodi va uning ta'limdagi o'rni. – T.: Ziyonet, 2020. – 128 b.
18. Inomova M.B. Loyiha asosida o'qitish metodologiyasi. – T.: TDPU nashriyoti, 2022. – 152 b.
19. Kember D., Leung D.Y.P., Jones A., Loke A.Y., McKay J., Sinclair K., Tse H., Webb C., Wong F.K.Y., Wong M. & Yeung E. Development of a Questionnaire to Measure the Level of Reflective Thinking // Assessment and Evaluation in Higher Education. – 2000. – Vol. 25, № 4. – P. 380-395.
20. Xoliqberdiyev K.X. O'qituvchi mahoratini oshirishda refleksiv yondashuv. – T.: Fan va texnologiya, 2017. – 160 b.